

MULTIVARIATE SPACE-TIME ESTIMATION OF HIDRAULIC HEAD, IN THE QUERÉTARO-OBRAJUELO VALLEY

GRACIELA HERRERA¹ AND EDGAR MENDOZA²

¹ *Instituto Mexicano de Tecnología del Agua, IMTA, Jiutepec, Morelos.*

gherrera@tlaloc.imta.mx

² *División de Estudios de Posgrado de la Facultad de Ingeniería, UNAM, Jiutepec, Morelos.*

edgaryuri@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this work a space-time method for multivariate estimation of hydraulic head was used, considering the hydraulic head in different years as different variables correlated in time. This type of method allows increasing the information used in the estimation of the hydraulic head for each year. The method was applied to estimate the hydraulic head in three different years in the aquifer Valle de Querétaro-Obrajuelo, Mexico, obtaining good results for cross validation and in the sense that when using the information of the three years jointly, some characteristics of the piezometric head configurations are clearly observed that are not when only the data of the considered year were used.

1. INTRODUCTION

The hydraulic head in an aquifer is a variable that is a function of both time and space. Frequently, when the analysis of its evolution is done it is found that the data is scarce and that not for all years data for the same wells are available. This makes difficult the analysis because for each year the estimation may be obtained with small information which results in a large uncertainty, and also because the estimate uncertainty for each year is different for different regions, which makes difficult to compare them.

In this work a space-time method for multivariate estimation was used, considering the hydraulic head in different years as different variables correlated in time. This type of method allows increasing the information used in the estimation of the hydraulic head for each year, and to diminish the differences in the estimate uncertainty between the different years.

Rouhani and Hall (1989) used a geostatistical approach to obtain a space-time estimate of the hydraulic head for the first time. In the geostatistical method applied, they considered time

as one additional coordinate to the spatial coordinates. But in their work they had some difficulties because they got singular matrices in the kriging system.

A second approach used to model space-time variables is to consider the process as a spatial group correlated in time or a group of time series correlated in space (Kyriakidis y Journel, 1999). Depending on the domain that has more samples. In this paper this approach is applied to estimate the hydraulic head at different dates in the Querétaro-Obrajuelo Valley, Mexico. To our knowledge this method was not applied before to estimate hydraulic heads in an aquifer.

The study area is located in the central portion of Mexico, it has a surface of 426 km², and it includes the Querétaro Valley and the Obrajuelo Valley.

2. GEOSTATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The steps followed for the geostatistical analysis of the data were: preliminary and exploratory data analysis, structural analysis, variable estimation and cross-validation, as described below. The package used for this analysis was GSLIB (Deutsch and Journel, 1998).

1.1 Preliminary analysis

This process consisted of classifying, ordering and integrating hydraulic head data in the aquifer for the years 1993, 1995 and 1999. For this purpose, a database was created which comprises a total of 185 wells distributed throughout the aquifer, with data regarding hydraulic head elevation, reporting a total of 89 well readings in 1993, 112 in 1995 and 75 wells in 1999.

1.2 Exploratory analysis

The exploratory analysis is based on conventional statistical techniques that allow to characterize the data. An exploratory analysis was conducted for each year data. The analyses began with determining the position and magnitude of the data values. For this, the measurement points were graphed with their respective values. Subsequently, a statistical analysis was performed. In addition, it was verified that the sample distribution was symmetrical. Table 1 shows the results of the statistical analysis. Because the original distributions were not normal, a data transformation was carried out. It consisted on subtracting the trend value to the data, to get what are called the residuals. The trend was calculated through ordinary least squares regression analysis, fitting a second-order polynomial. Table 1 also shows the statistics for the residuals. As it can be seen, the symmetry improves very much with the transformation of the data.

1.3 Structural analysis

The purpose of this step is to determine the spatial structure of the data. With this end, the experimental semivariogram and the experimental cross-semivariograms were determined.

For the experimental semivariogram there are a group of functions that satisfy the requirements of a valid semivariogram, which are called authorized models. An authorized model was proposed for the experimental semivariogram through a fitting process.

TABLE 1. Hydraulic head and residual statistics.

Year	1993	1995	1999	1993 residual	1995 residual	1999 residual
Number of data	85	112	75	85	112	75
Mean	1737.35	1728.37	1720.65	-2.0E-6	-3.0E-6	4.74E-17
Median	1713.48	1706.89	1693.65	2.82	0.54	0.75
Standard deviation	58.12	54.46	62.15	28.64	27.42	30.71
Minimum	1640.42	1629.24	1623.33	-90.29	-92.66	-89.44
Maximum	1894.43	1892.48	1890.40	79.13	89.45	83.74
Curtosis	1.64	2.72	1.55	1.57	2.02	1.37
Asymmetry coefficient	1.60	1.84	1.55	-0.39	-0.05	-0.11
	Sever asymmetry	Sever asymmetry	Sever asymmetry	Light asymmetry	Symmetry	Symmetry

To fit the experimental cross-semivariogram a linear model of coregionalization was used (Goovaerts, 1997). It is defined as a set of direct and cross semivariogram models $\gamma_{ij}(h)$, such that

$$\gamma_{ij}(h) = \sum_{u=0}^{N_s} b_{ij}^u g_u(h) \quad \forall i, j,$$

where each $g_u(h)$ is an authorized semivariogram model, and the $N_s + 1$ matrices of coefficients b_{ij}^u are all positive semidefinite. The results of the structural analysis are summarized on Figure 1.

1.4 Cross validation

The cross validation method was used to validate the semivariogram models. This method consists on taking out one element of the sample at a time and estimating the value on that point using kriging, with the fitted semivariogram model. The error e_i is calculated through the difference of the data and the estimate at the point x_i . The errors calculated in this work

were the mean error ($ME = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_i$), the square mean error ($SME = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (e_i)^2$), which have

to be close to zero, and the square mean standard error ($SMSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(e_i)^2}{\sigma_i^2}$), which has to be

close to one. The results are shown on table 2. The absolute value of the error mean augments

with the cokriging method for all years but the square mean error and the quadratic mean standard error for this method have closer values to what the theory indicates, with exception of the SME for 1995 which increases for cokriging.

FIGURE 1. Experimental and theoretical semivariograms for 1995, 1999 and 1993 with their cross semivariograms.

Table 2. Cross-validation results.

Method and year	Error		
	EM	SME	SMSE
Ordinary kriging, 1993	-0.19	390.55	0.82
Ordinary kriging, 1995	-0.10	252.34	0.80
Ordinary kriging, 1999	-0.40	426.3	0.80
Cokriging, 1993	-0.79	349.51	0.92
Cokriging, 1995	-1.63	284.31	0.99
Cokriging, 1999	-1.96	309.03	0.95

1.5 Estimation

In the estimation of the hydraulic head, ordinary kriging was used for the univariate case, and cokriging for the multivariate case. The estimate was calculated for a regular mesh of 41 columns by 51 rows, with a cell size of 1,100 m by 1,100 m.

The results are shown on Figures 2, 3 and 4, for the years, 1993, 1995, and 1999, respectively. There are significant differences between the hydraulic estimates obtained with the two methods. Graphically, it can be observed a better match between the equipotential curves and the data for cokriging than for kriging.

FIGURE 2. a) Ordinary kriging 1993, b) Cokriging 1993.

FIGURE 3. a) Ordinary kriging 1995, b) Cokriging 1995.

FIGURE 4. a) Ordinary kriging 1999, b) Cokriging 1999.

Also, to use the data of the different years as auxiliary information allows a smoother representation in the areas with few data. The greater differences are shown in the zone in which Laguna el Salitre is located, there a water divide can be identified on the cokriging estimates that is not observed clearly on the kriging estimates. These differences are a result of the additional data that are used to estimate the hydraulic head for each one of these years.

3. CONCLUSION

The analysis presented shows that for the Querétaro-Obrajuelo aquifer it may be useful estimating the hydraulic head in a given year using as auxiliary variables the hydraulic head on those years considered in the analysis closer to it. A disadvantage when using this method is the increase in the number of semivariograms and cross-semivariograms that have to be calculated ($n(n+1)/2$, where n is the number of variables to be analyzed).

REFERENCES

- Deutsch, C. V., and A. G. Journel, *GSLIB: Geostatistical Software Library and User's Guide*, Oxford Univ. Press, New York, 1998.
- Goovaerts, P., *Geostatistics natural resources evaluation*, Oxford Univ. Press, New York, 1997.
- Kyriakidis, P. C. and A. G. Journel, Geostatistical space-time models: A review, *Mathematical Geology*, Vol 31, 6, 651-684, 1999.
- Rouhani, S. and T. Hall, Space-time kriging of groundwater data, in M. Armstrong, ed., *Geostatistics*, vol. 2: Kluwer Academic Publ., Dordrecht, 639-650, 1989.